

typing and phylogenetic analysis of the gene *inmp*, coding an integral membrane protein, distinguished AlmWB-associated phytoplasma strains originating from diverse host plants, whereas their 16S rRNA, *tufB* and *groEL* genes shared 100% sequence identity. Moreover, dN/dS analysis indicated positive selection acting on *inmp* gene. Draft genome analyses suggest a parasitism based on the import of glycerol-3-phosphate, a critical mobile inducer of plant systemic immunity. Additionally, integral membrane proteins, effector-like proteins and potential candidates for interaction with hosts were identified. One of the integral membrane proteins was predicted as BI-1, an inhibitor of apoptosis-promoting Bax factor. Bioinformatics analyses revealed the presence of putative BI-1 in draft and complete genomes of other '*Ca. Phytoplasma*' species. The genetic diversity within '*Ca. P. phoenicium*' strain populations in Lebanon suggested that AlmWB disease could be associated with phytoplasma strains derived from the adaptation of an original strain to diverse hosts. Moreover, the identification of BI-1 in '*Ca. P. phoenicium*' draft genome and within genomes of other '*Ca. Phytoplasma*' species suggested its potential role as a phytoplasma fitness-increasing factor by modification of the host-defense response.

THE NEW DEAL IN VIRUS DISCOVERY: A MAJOR CONCERN FOR "MINOR" CROPS. M. Morelli, M. Chiumentì, P. Saldarelli, A. Giampetruzzi, A. Minafra. *National Research Council of Italy, Institute for Sustainable Plant Protection (IPSP), Via G. Amendola 122/D, I-70126 Bari, Italy. E-mail: massimiliano.morelli@ipsp.cnr.it*

The use of NGS approach allowed the identification and the complete genome characterization of several plant virus species, previously unknown (*Persimmon cryptic virus*, PeCV; *Mulberry badnavirus-1*, MBV-1), or scarcely characterized and never associated to a specific symptomatology and/or host (*Persimmon rhabdovirus A*, PeVA; *Apple green crinkle associated virus*, AGCaV). Significantly, these findings arose from crops, respectively Japanese persimmon (*Diospyros kaki*) in the case of PeCV and PeVA, quince (*Cydonia oblonga*) for AGCaV and mulberry (*Morus alba*) for MBV-1, disregarded in traditional quest for viral agents and diseases. Routinely used bio- and molecular assays, however modern they are, always hide an *a priori* choice for target, influenced by evident symptomatology, diagnostic purposes prone to certification standard enquiries, availability of literature, etc. NGS analysis, being apart from such constraints, gives the opportunity to widen the target range, thus including also cultivated and wild crops, so far considered not agronomically relevant, or never characterized for their sanitary status. The new approach, accounting on a better feasibility and reliability of detection performance, is leading to noteworthy steps forward for plant virology studies addressed to characterize minor crop infections. A rising number of new species discovered, in once misinvestigated temperate and tropical fruit crops, should not be merely regarded in terms of basic research accomplishments. The meaningful contribution of NGS advent in this field relies in a potential of innovative knowledge to be expended, for instance, in upgrading the extant certification schemes, tracking unforeseen threats in propagative material exchanges and setting new attribution rules for a challenging taxonomical allocation of oncoming species or strains.

SYNTHETIC CLONES OF GRAPEVINE ALGERIAN LATENT VIRUS (GALV) DEVELOP A TYPICAL TOMBUSVIRUS INFECTION IN NICOTIANA BENTHAMIANA INFECTED CELLS. A. Lovato¹, A. Polverari¹, D. Maffi², F. Faoro². ¹Department of Biotechnology, University of Verona, Strada le Grazie 15, I-37134 Verona, Italy. ²Department of Agricultural and Environmental Sciences - Production, Landscape, Agroenergy (DISAA), University of

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GALV is a 30 nm icosahedral virus (*Tombusvirus* genus), with a positive ssRNA genome of 4731 nucleotides including at least five Open Reading Frames (ORFs) encoding for replicase proteins (p33 and p92), the coat protein (p40), the movement protein (p24) and the multifunctional p19 protein, which also functions as a silencing suppressor. We have previously produced a synthetic GALV construct complying with the available genome sequence of a GALV isolate from nippelfruit (GALV-nf). This clone systemically infected both grapevine and *Nicotiana benthamiana* plants causing severe symptoms. In order to use GALV-nf as a VIGS (Virus Induced Gene Silencing) vector, we modified it by a single nucleotide substitution on the p19 ORF, to reduce the silencing suppressor activity of the virus, hence increasing the plant silencing efficiency against a target gene. The cytopathology of this mutant (GALV-nf-Δ) and the unmodified clone have been compared to verify if a less functional p19 allowed a correct, though reduced, virus synthesis. Ultrastructural analysis revealed the presence of isometric virus particles and multivesicular bodies (MVBs), typical of tombusviruses, in the apical leaves infected with either GALV clones but more consistent in GALV-nf infection. MVBs mainly originated from peroxisomes, though it cannot be excluded that also mitochondria could be involved in their formation. Immunogold labelling using an anti p33 serum showed that viral replicase is mainly located in the peripheral membrane of MVBs in both synthetic virus constructs, demonstrating that p19 modification does not affect GALV localization and replication but strongly interferes in terms of virus virulence.

DIPLODIA SAPINEA AND CLIMATE CHANGE: SPECIES DISTRIBUTION MODELS OF THE MOST IMPORTANT PINE SHOOT PATHOGEN IN ITALY. L. Bosso¹, H. Rebelo^{2,3}, N. Luchi⁴, G. Maresi⁵, D. Russo^{1,3}, G. Cristinzio¹. ¹Department of Agricultural Sciences, University of Napoli "Federico II", Via Università 100, I-80055 Portici (NA), Italy. ²CIBIO-Centro de Investigacao em Biodiversidade e Recursos Genéticos da Universidade do Porto, Campus Agrário de Vairão, R. Padre Armando QuintasVairão, Portugal. ³School of Biological Sciences, University of Bristol 24, Tyndall Avenue, BS8 1TQ, Bristol, United Kingdom. ⁴National Research Council of Italy, Institute for Sustainable Plant Protection (IPSP), Via Madonna del Piano 10, I-50019 Sesto Fiorentino (FI), Italy. ⁵Technology Transfer Centre, Edmund Mach Foundation, Via E. Mach 1, I-38010 San Michele all'Adige (TN), Italy. E-mail: luciano.bosso@unina.it

Species Distribution Models (SDMs) provide realistic scenarios to explain the influence of bioclimatic variables on plant pathogens distribution. In this study, we develop a maximum entropy model for *Diplodia sapinea* in Italy to reach the following goals: i) to carry out the first geographical distribution analysis in Italy and determine which Eco-Geographical Variables (EGVs) may affect its distribution; ii) to detect the effect of climate change on the species' geographic range by 2050 and 2070. To develop SDMs for *D. sapinea* we used Maxent vers. 3.3.3k, the most popular approach to model species distributions with scarce presence-only data. Future climate projections for *D. sapinea* were derived from six Global Climate Models (GCMs) (BCC-CSM1-1, CCSM4, GISS-E2-R, MIROC5, HadGEM2-ES, MPI-ESM-LR) for two representative concentration pathways (RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5) and two time projections: 2050 and 2070. The most important EGVs for the current distribution were found to be land cover, altitude and mean temperature of wettest quarter. The distribution of *D. pinea* essentially increased in Central and Southern Italy and shifted upwards by 90m. Moreover, this fungus expanded its range in response to an increase in mean temperature of wettest and driest quarter in all GCMs of 1.9 and 5°C, respectively. Validation statistics (AUC, AUC_{diff} TSS) showed that